

The Relationship of Anthocyanins with Color of Organically and Conventionally Cultivated Potatoes

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Abstract : Many of the compounds present in potato are important because of their beneficial effects on health, therefore, are highly desirable in the human diet. Potato tubers contain significant amounts of anthocyanins. The aim of this research was to determine the content of anthocyanins and its relationship with the colour of organically and conventionally cultivated potato varieties. In the research eight potato samples of three potato varieties were analysed on anthocyanins, dry matter content and colour. Obtained results show that there was no significant influence on amount of anthocyanins between different cultivation environments ($p>0.05$) while between varieties-significant difference ($p<0.05$). Strong correlation between the amount of anthocyanins and colour was determined.

Keywords : potato variety, anthocyanins, organic, conventional, dry matter

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